

Interview with Marta María Albert Márquez

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1. What strengths do you see in the partnership between B²-InF and URJC?

The Rey Juan Carlos is a young university with enormous research potential. As a member of the project, the University has been able to form a research team with specialists in all the areas that our legal analysis required: bio-law, patients' law, advertising, commercial information, advertising soft law, public international law and more. Moreover, the University has a master's degree in bioethics, which starts its fourteenth promotion in September, placing our University at the forefront of bioethics research at the national and international levels.

By forming part of B2-InF, our University will be able to advance in its internationalization process, strengthening alliances with other European universities and research centres. We also hope this partnership will be fruitful in the future when the accumulated experience in disseminating and transferring the knowledge generated by this project will lead to the consolidation of a new way of scientific research.

2. Is the project able to address all legal aspects of its research?

We must bear in mind that the legal aspects we addressed in the project are twofold: what information citizens have and how the information reaches them through the clinics. On the one hand, we start from an analysis of the legislation and jurisprudence on medically assisted reproduction in each of the eight countries we have worked on (in terms of legislation, we stick to that issued by the Constitutional Courts in the countries where they exist, or, failing that, to that given by the highest national judiciary). On the other hand, national regulations on commercial information or advertising, which clinics must respect in configuring their websites, are also of great relevance. The so-called "soft law" plays a decisive role here, i.e. sectoral self-regulation, which has worked more than well in the past.

To all of this must be added the perspective of international law, fundamentally that of the case law of the European Court of Human Rights in Strasbourg, belonging to the Council of Europe, of which all the states we are researching in the project are members except Kosovo.

Are we in a position to cover all the legal aspects of assisted human reproduction and the information that reaches the public about it? There are probably aspects that we do not or cannot address with all the dedication they deserve. Our focus is conditioned by the design of the research itself and, fundamentally, by the concerns and interests of young Europeans regarding the legal status of assisted reproduction in Europe. This area is undoubtedly addressed in detail in our research. But it could be argued that practically all relevant legal aspects are addressed in our analysis. Either because they directly constitute an object of concern for citizens or by omission. If a relevant legal issue is not experienced by citizens, there is also room for research and analysis on the reasons justifying this gap.

3. How do you think our guidelines will have to tackle the many differences in the legal aspects of fertility care across Europe?

The differences in the regulations on the use of the techniques in the different European countries exist (in some aspects they are, moreover, very significant), and we must remember that, in this matter, each European State retains sovereignty to regulate them in one way or another. I believe that we should aim for regulation with as few disparities as possible at the European level. Ideally, towards a "common space" in assisted human reproduction, based on the values and principles shared by European citizens on which we intend to establish our political coexistence.

It goes without saying that assisted human reproduction brings some very "sensitive" issues to the table, and we do not intend to ignore this in our recommendations. However, it is also true that the research carried out within the framework of the project has highlighted the need to harmonize the various European legislations. This is a demand of European youth which cannot be ignored but which cannot be resolved immediately or without the necessary reflection. Therefore, our recommendations often point to the need to open public debates on issues of equal concern to young Europeans, such as fair access to techniques, the regulation of donors, and the risk of a eugenic drift in applying techniques. In my opinion, this perception of the exact social needs to be met, of the same legal assets to be protected, should be the starting point for moving towards harmonization of the legal regime for assisted human reproduction in Europe. And I am pleased that our project aims to clarify what young people need and demand because this research is essential, as I am trying to explain, to set this process of legislative harmonization in motion.

4. Is the young society's perception of fertility and treatments a topic of importance from the legal point of view? Why so?

The relationship between law and society is a two-way street. Law generates social change, and society demands legal change. From the latter point of view, the opinion of young people is fundamental because the law must be sensitive to these social demands, especially those of the youngest citizens, who are the present and the future of our societies. But unfortunately, the legislator sometimes fails to grasp these demands and needs. I believe that, in this sense, our project can be of great use to all political actors insofar as it acts as a loudspeaker for the concerns of our young people regarding assisted human reproduction and fertility in general.

But there is also the other direction of the law-society dynamic. Law has an enormous potential to change mentalities, normalize certain behaviours, making citizens consider "good" what "legal is". Therefore, in our recommendations, we consider it fundamental to sensitize and raise awareness among the younger population about the fundamental ethical and legal principles issues involved in the application of the techniques, at least in those aspects where a European consensus can be mentioned at the ethical-legal level. For this reason, the case law of the ECtHR is also central to our analysis insofar as it provides us with a reflection of what these basic principles and values are and how they are applied to the regulation of ARTs.

Of course, within the European framework, many control mechanisms work well in limiting any hypothetical action of political power contrary to the human rights enshrined in the European Convention on Human Rights. But what better than a young public opinion robustly formed in this nucleus of shared values to guarantee a European legislation fully aligned with them in the future?

5. The voice of society is essential in this domain. So why do you think it has been relatively neglected so far?

Tough question. I only dare to point out a few ideas that may explain the legislator's relative deafness to social demands in this field.

Firstly, the legislation of assisted human reproduction techniques is a privileged field for "social engineering", that is, the legislator's prerogative to shape a new social mentality, to re-educate the population (which is a potent tool of social control and generates well-known problems in the dynamics of any democracy). But, in the end, the regulation of assisted human reproduction points to fundamental anthropological and ethical questions.

Secondly, concerning reproductive medical care, technical issues sometimes arise that are difficult for the general public to understand, and where an extra effort of education is needed to create a well-formed public opinion within which a fierce debate on some ethical and legal dilemmas surrounding assisted human reproduction can be launched. This effort in forming a general view is very much present in our recommendations. But unfortunately, it involves a significant investment in time, effort and money that public authorities are not always willing to make.

We have also seen how young people sometimes lack concerns about issues that are dealt with in detail in the law, as is the case in some countries with supernumerary embryos, e.g. When there is no social culture on a subject, what opinion can the legislator take into account? Public opinion remains on the sidelines because the concern does not exist. That opinion must first be formed, and the tools must be provided for it to exist. This is a primary point of our recommendations.

6. What is your opinion about the project?

It seems to me that one of its strengths is that all members are very clear about what our goals are and how to achieve them. Our fundamental objective is to give citizens a voice to improve ARTs for Society by researching the representations of the general population and comparing them with the information provided by the clinics to society.

Both the perceptions of the citizens and the information provided by the clinics are analyzed from a gender, socio-cultural, and legal point of view, with the idea of delivering valuable recommendations for both policymakers and the clinics themselves so that the voice of European citizens is genuinely heard on the most relevant issues of medically assisted reproduction. Each team works according to the methodology specific to its research field. Even within the thematic analysis, the working method has its specificities. For example, we must necessarily start from a legal framework that must be clarified and studied beforehand to carry out our analysis based on it.

But what is decisive is the overall result. The research is based on a well-thought-out and very precise design. The partners cover all the aspects of the area that need to be studied. I believe that the guidelines that will be the final result of our project will become an essential tool for the actors involved in assisted reproduction in Europe: policymakers, clinics, and researchers... contributing to filling a gap in the knowledge base of the European assisted reproduction field: the real needs of European society and, in particular, of its youngest members, in the area of fertility and assisted human reproduction.